

Beyond the horizon: High Frequency Surface Wave Radar

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present a high-level view of the High Frequency Surface Wave Radar developed for the Radars for long distance maritime surveillance and SAR operations (RANGER) project ([1]). The over-the-horizon radar proposes a new system architecture, with new waveforms, new processing methods, and new antenna concepts to provide solutions to meet HFSWR (High Frequency Surface Wave Radar) challenges as increasing the long range distance detection for small vessels with improved accuracy.

Keywords: Over-the-horizon (OTH) Radar; High Frequency (HF) Surface Wave Radar (SWR); maritime surveillance; Radar Cross Section (RCS)

1. INTRODUCTION

The potential offered by HF surface wave radars for maritime surveillance and in particular for the entire Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), is a sea area for a state which has rights from its baseline out to 200 nautical miles from the coast defined by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea in 1982[2], has recently been rediscovered, with the overhaul of national strategies related to security and surveillance of the maritime environment. Thus, over the past decade or so, the evolution of the strategic context has led to international instability, primarily affecting fragile states, promoting illicit and violent activities, generating potential risks for societies as: security threats, caused by trafficking (narcotics, psychotropic substances, weapons), illegal transport of migrants, maritime terrorism and piracy, have replaced the military threat. At the same time, the economic activities carried out by sea have increased very significantly, proportionally much higher than the increase in world economic development [3]. This development requires a stronger presence of coastal States to ensure and strengthen safety and security at sea.

One of the main challenges of HF radar industry is to provide a technology able to manage physics specific constraints of HF band. Conception of an efficient HF radar solution requires management of the following physical aspects:

- Propagation loss: It is affected by the sea conductivity (function of salinity and temperature) and land-sea transitions (island on the covered area).
- Sea clutter: it is a noise composed of all parasite echoes generated by sea surface irregularities.
- Ionospheric clutter: it is a noise composed of self-generated interferences via sky wave propagation.
- HF noise: It is a versatile environmental noise in HF band (atmospheric noise, galactic noise, man-made noise). It is seasonal and also has high day/night variation. The HF noise level variation at a given time around the globe is of around 20dB.
- Spectral congestion in HF band.

DIGINEXT's achievements within the RANGER framework take into account its background in the HF radar as well as its existing sites. Nevertheless, the new radar developed (HFSWR type) needed new technical concepts to be refined and to support itself on other technological bricks which go further than this first accomplishment in order to give answer to RANGER's broken objectives.

DIGINEXT's contributions in the field are numerous:

- Develop a system which allows small dimension boats to be detected (and/or of weak Surface Radar Equivalent) within long range. On the French sites, performances must be optimized for maximum efficiency; this is accomplished through numerous transmitting antennas, and a stronger transmission power level.
- Design and develop a deployable system on remote areas and capable of taking into account the interference caused by the islands. This system will introduce limited performances, coherent with the budget of this project, however it will allow evaluating the HFSWR systems' performances surrounded by the Greek archipelago's islands masking boats' radars.

Figure 1: Global view of HF Surface Wave Radar

In order to answer to these objectives, diverse factors will be taken into account:

- Use of a secondary transmission frequency which allows simultaneously:
- To integrate the interference masks due to the reflectivity of the sea and the ionosphere, producing pertinent information for detection.
- To provide complementary information on the Radar cross section of small sized boats.
- An antenna array development allowing to improve performances.

2. SIMULATOR

Before its implementation, the capability of an HF radar needs to be evaluated to validate the potential of installation sites. The HF radar simulator is a software intended to allow the evaluation of the performances of one radar configuration in its environment of exploitation.

2.2 Simulator's specifications

The objective of this software is to allow the user to know in advance and in an intuitive way the parameters of coverage and the level of detection performances concerning a radar installation. The user can then study / modify the various accessible components of the radar in the simulator to obtain a configuration which responds to the established needs according to the following constraints:

- coverage area,
- expected capacity of detection in distance according to the ship sizes,
- available or necessary frequency bands for the operation of the system,
- radiated power available or required for the operation of the system,

Figure 2: Simulator description

The simulation software (summarizes with the figure 2) produces a set of results that can be evaluated by the user. For every tested configuration the user knows the detection capabilities of the sensor in the area according to:

- the boat categories with the Radar cross section (RCS) and their particularities in HF band,
- the ground conductivity of the sites (transmitting and receiving)
- the sea state and its roughness: The classical model for the roughness of the sea is based on the studies of D. Barrick **Error! Reference source not found.**. This model takes into account the impact of the wind direction versus the propagation.
- the seasons and their specific electromagnetic noises (night and day) in HF band **Error! Reference source not found.**
- the impact of the geography on the covered zone with the natural or artificial obstacles (though the Millington model).

2.2 RCS study

The Radar Cross Section (RCS) is a key parameter of the radar equation. It determines greatly the radar performances. The RCS of an object is specific to each radar frequency especially in the HF band. Knowing RCS of maritime target makes possible to:

- estimate performance for a particular radar configuration
- optimize radar setup for particular kind of target.

With High Frequency Surface Wave (HFSW) Radar it is very difficult to accurately measure RCS for different type of vessel. Moreover it is quite impossible to make measurements in laboratory (anechoic chamber) because of the required dimensions. It is why we choose to estimate RCS by simulation. RCS is calculated with the software “CST Micro Wave Studio EM solver”. The transient solver was chosen for the RCS simulations. 3D-model of ship is taken from different kind of sources. Most of the models are downloaded from internet under free user license.

Figure 3: Simulated RCS (red) and received powers

The RCS simulations have been validated with different known trajectories based on their AIS (Automatic Identification System) data transmitted by the vessels. The figure 3 displays the adequacy between the received power by the HF Radar for a ferry (200 m length) and its RCS simulation at 4.5 MHz. It is to note that based on these simulation for several frequencies from 4 MHz to 10 MHz, the RCS vary significantly depending on the chosen one and on the radar angle of view or can be very flat depending on the vessel's dimensions. These results are to be merged with the surface wave's propagation losses for selecting the appropriate frequency.

The figure 4 shows the general view of the simulator interface with the different configuration tools or information zones which are available.

Figure 4: Simulator's general view

The figure 5 shows the Millington modeling (for the sea-land propagation losses) applied over the Aegean Sea for the 2 frequencies used for the RANGER's Pilots.

Figure 5: Island's impact

On the left picture is illustrated the E-field from the Rx point of view at 4.5 MHz and, at 9.3 MHz on the right. For both cases, the impact of islands appears clearly just behind them, but in addition, there is an increase of loss for 9.3MHz frequency (around 10 dB).

3. ENVIRONMENTAL INTEGRATION

High accuracy for radars is synonym of high constraints on technical specifications. The first ones to come to mind are the size of the antenna networks and the power of the transmitters; however, the main one is the spectrum availability. In parallel, environmental rules, like urbanism and electromagnetic exposure, exist without any considerations about radar needs. As a consequence, the design of a new type of radar has to balance between technical constraints and regulations. The approach is structured in 3 domains.

3.1 Spectrum

The list order is pragmatic: Spectrum is the fundamental parameter for the best performance and it defines the radar's parameters to take into account to work safe and to be well integrated in the environment.

Radio waves have been in use for a long time, spectrum occupancy is high and the introduction of a new type of radar needs to take into account existing services and their international priority. The organizations in charge of the spectrum are:

- International Telecommunication Union –Recommendation (ITU-R) for international level
- European Administrations for regional level (Europe)
- National administration

Practically, it is the national administration who wishes to implant a radar which manages the search for frequency allocation. The European Conference of Postal and Telecommunications Administrations (CEPT) coordinates the frequency assignment between them and can develop rules of sharing at European level. Work starts with its national frequency table, followed by an analysis of regional agreements. All the process is based on the methodology and international agreements of the shared frequencies defined in the ITU-R **Error! Reference source not found.** The variety of the applications of radiolocation has forced ITU to define technical criteria to help cohabitation in the various wavebands (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

3.2 Safety at work and around

A minimum requirement for the developed equipment is to respect the European directives on the subjects of conformity and security, which correspond to a civil use of the radars. However, the specificity of the use of RANGER radars could involve a deployment on military bases or platforms which have particular specifications (sensitivity of the weapons to the electromagnetic fields, for example). A thorough analysis must be carried out within the framework of the project to determine the standard levels to follow to achieve the most adapted one for the operational deployment of the radar.

Regarding the phase of prototyping, for the Exposure of workers to electromagnetic fields, the working conditions around HFSWR radar must respect directive **Error! Reference source not found.** on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (electromagnetic fields). System is designed to avoid direct contact current. For electric and magnetic fields, in operation, the safe guard distance for workers is less than 5 meters from each antenna. Therefore worker can access the antenna array keeping the above mentioned restriction.

For the Public exposure to electromagnetic fields, each EU Member State is responsible for providing adequate health protection for its citizens and for deciding on measures to be implemented. However, to support Member States and to ensure the highest level of health protection for European citizens, the EU asks governments to assess exposure to electromagnetic fields and to take appropriate action when reference levels are exceeded – as laid down in COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION of 12 July 1999 on the limitation of exposure of the general public to electromagnetic fields from 0 Hz to 300 GHz **Error! Reference source not found.**

3.3 Environment

Installation of a new type of radar equipment need a large surface of flat ground being able to reach 1000m of length, and the proximity with the coast for HF radar. The rare places being able to correspond to the preceding criteria are often close to those protected to ensure the safeguard of biodiversity **Error! Reference source not found.** The two French sites of the OTH radar are installed in activity in Natura 2000 area. They passed the authorization process by limiting the footprint of the antenna arrays, being careful of existing plants and taking into account reproduction period to plan the building of sites.

4. HFSW Radar

The general development of the HFSW radar, during the RANGER project, is the use of 2 simultaneous frequencies and the application of the multiplicative principle for the beamforming using 2 independent receiving antenna arrays.

4.1 French installation

The HF Radar is installed in a bi-static configuration and for the French case on three sites:

- The transmitting site is composed of 16 antennas but divided in 2 sub-arrays for using two frequencies:
 - 10 antennas for the first frequency
 - 6 antennas for the second frequency
- The receiving site is composed of 2 subarrays
 - One main array with up to 32 antennas
 - A second additional sub-arrays with 8 antennas for the multiplicative beamforming principle

The Rx antenna arrays are installed in a salt-march (Natura 2000 areas) in compliance environmental constraints.

Figure 6: Rx antennas in French's installation

- The Control Room site is linked to the other RANGER components such as the Uniform Communication Gateway (UCG) through the OTH (or HF) Gateway.

The figure 9 summarizes this HFSWR configuration for the 2nd RANGER French Pilot.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of the French HF Radar configuration

The ionospheric reflection is a self-interferer that can reduce the detection capability in specific areas of the Doppler/Distance map. The design of the antenna arrays (Tx and Rx), combined with a specific process for the antenna's weightings, allow to decrease the impact of the Ionospheric clutter. It is to note that the mitigation is applied on the both sites (Tx and Rx).

Figure 10: Ionospheric clutter: Before and after mitigation

The OTH detection capabilities during the RANGER's 2nd French Pilot (figure 11), with only a sum of 300W as amplifiers power output (per lobe) splitted on 10 transmitting antennas, are up to 230 km (125 NM) for the smaller vessels (between 10 m and 30 m length) and above 320 km (170 NM) for the bigger vessels (above 30 m length) or beyond for some cases, with a detection ratio of 90%.

Figure 11: HFSWR Tracks with the 170 NM coverage map

4.2 Greek installation

The Greek HF Radar is also in a bistatic configuration. The crossing of both patterns (Tx and Rx) defines the coverage area of the Radar. The range of the coverage depends on the radar's link budget, that means the signal power amplification and Tx/Rx gains mainly but also the number of antennas on the both sites.

In the case of the Geek RANGER Pilot, the HF configuration is reduced compared to the French installation:

- o 3 antennas for the transmission site
- o 16 active antennas for the reception site

The optimization of antennas positioning as well as their weightings has been realized as in the French case.

Based on these developments, the coverage for these reduced installations is illustrated with the figure 12.

Figure 12: HFSWR coverage for the reduced installation and low power in Greek area

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a high-level view of the Over-The-Horizon radar developed for the long range detection taking into account the interference from islands in the propagation wave. The system is currently being developed in the context of the European project RANGER and is going to be validated in several pilot scenarios in the Mediterranean Sea.

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